

(0.01M) in 5 ml of water. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a sand-bath for 3 hr and 50 ml of water was added to it at room temperature. The resulting product was then filtered and crystallised from acetic acid in white fine crystals. In the same way other bis-derivatives required for the synthesis of diquinolyl methanes are obtained.

(II) 2,2', 4,4'-Tetrahydroxy-3,3'-diquinolyl methane : Methylene bis(cyanacetanilide) (3.329; 0.1M) was dissolved in a clear solution of polyphosphoric acid prepared by dissolving phosphorous pentoxide (20.0 g) in phosphoric acid (12.0 ml, d. 1.75), and the reaction mixture was heated in an oil bath at 140° for 3 hr with a calcium chloride guard tube. After cooling, hydrochloric acid (60 ml, 1N) was added and the mixture was neutralized with sodium hydroxide solution (pH 4), when the crude product was precipitated. It was then filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. The diquinolyl methane derivatives listed in table 2 are accordingly synthesised.

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Stabilities of some Heterocyclic Amine Complexes : Part II.

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IN the previous communication¹ formation constants of Ni(II), Cd(II) and Mg(II) complexes with pyridine and monomethyl pyridines have been discussed. Structure of nickel complexes has also

been studied². In the present work the reactions between Ni(II) and di- and tri-methyl pyridines (2:4-lutidine, 2:6-lutidine and 2:4:6-collidine) have been studied in aqueous solution. Ni(II) complexes of lutidine in non-aqueous solvents have been studied earlier³.

Materials and Methods : The inorganic compounds were all BDH(A.R.) or Fluka pure quality. The ligands were, however, purified by fractional distillation and the purity was tested by finding out the boiling points. Double distilled water was used for preparing all the solutions.

A Metrohm pH meter model E 350A was used which reads up to the accuracy of ± 0.05 . A constant temperature bath was used to maintain constant temperature, its accuracy being $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

The proton ligand and metal ligand formation constants at 35° and 45° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$) have been determined by Irving-Rossotti's two titration techniques⁴ as detailed in the previous paper¹. Log K_1 and log K_2 values obtained from the formation curves have been improved by use of successive approximation method⁵. The values have been tabulated in Table I and have an accuracy of ± 0.05 .

Discussion

The experimental data reveals that the stabilities of the complexes are in the order of 2:4-lutidine complex < 2:6-lutidine complex < 2:4:6-collidine complex which is in accordance with the basicities of the ligands (2:4-lutidine < 2:6-lutidine < 2:4:6-collidine). Exact linear relationship⁵, however, does not hold good. This may be attributed to the difference in $M-N\pi$ interaction, entropy and enthalpy changes in the formation of different complexes. Nickel(II), being a transition metal ion with d^8 configuration, has filled $d\pi$ orbitals and can affect interaction with the $p\pi$ orbital over the nitrogen atom of the tertiary base molecule. The extent of $M-L\pi$ interaction differs depending on the number and position of the $-CH_3$ group introduced in the ring. Lutidine complexes are more stable than pyridine and picoline complexes as expected from higher basicities of the lutidines. With the increase in temperature the basicities of the ligands go down and there is corresponding decrease in the formation constants as seen in Table I.

TABLE I

	P_{KH}		$\log K_1$		$\log K_2$		$\Delta \log P_{KH}$	$\Delta \log \beta_2$
	35°	45°	35°	45°	35°	45°		
Diaquo bis 2:4 lutidine Nickel (II)	6.44	6.32	3.26	3.14	2.67	2.56	0.12	0.23
Diaquo bis 2:6 lutidine Nickel (II)	6.61	6.53	3.32	3.25	2.77	2.70	0.07	0.14
Diaquo bis 2:4:6 collidine Nickel (II)	6.93	6.80	3.56	3.43	2.99	2.88	0.13	0.24

NOTES

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It is regretted that due to oversight the paper entitled :

Terpenoids Part LXII : New Synthesis of 2,6-Dimethyl-3,6-epoxyoct-7-enol (\pm)-Lilac Alcohol

published in the January 1973 issue of this journal has been printed again in its February issue.

p. 141 for Title Read

End Group of Polymethyl Methacrylate Obtained by Initiation with Permanganate Organic Acid Redox Pair